

Repressive and Preventive Synthesis Model in Anti-Corruption of Bureaucracy in Indonesia

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Abstract: This study attempted to provide a solution to eradicate corruption by using a model approach repression and prevention THATEE Model. The writing method using a literature review in explaining some of the facts of corruption in the New Order era and reform. The results show that the discussion of actual corruption can be eradicated by using synthesis the KPPH Model and THATEE Model. THATEE Model is a formula based on a series of corruption preventive action formulated in the form of trust, honest, transparency, education and ethics with the involvement of state actors (government, legislative and stakeholder coalition) will strengthen the eradication of corruption in the future. While the model is a formula KPPH repressive against corruption formulated in a series of actions the commitment of law enforcement, political will and international cooperation and even the death penalty to be an alternative to combat the growing proliferation of corruption in this country with severe punishments for the corrupt. The study is expected to contribute thoughts and preventive and repressive measures against corruption in Indonesia in support of law enforcement against attorneys, judges, the judicial mafia, the authorities, employers and political elite in Indonesia.

Key words: Synthesis model, repressive, preventive, anti-corruption, udges, education

INTRODUCTION

In the history of corruption in Indonesia, in 1977 gives some special notes about cases of corruption handled law enforcement officers. Several agencies throughout Indonesia prosecutor noted that corruption amounts to 513 cases with state losses of IDR 4 billion more. In 1978, had risen to 721 cases with state losses amounting to IDR 30 billion more. Thus, the average year-on-year figure was rising steadily. Then in 1984 where there were 1,371 corruption cases handled by the state losses of IDR 135 billion more. Especially for South Sulawesi, South Sulawesi prosecutor succeeded in uncovering cases of corruption were 245 cases within the last 3 years in a row, the state losses of IDR 29 billion (Lopa, 2002).

This is a picture of corruption, not only in power but in any area in the New Order corruption is endemic to sign in local governance. New Order's corruption is not only done by Soeharto as the highest authority but the people around him with the same shape. The forms of corruption made by people close to them rely on family, relatives and the interests of other entrepreneurs. Soeharto error is too trusting aides and a lack of supervision of the officials who hold strategic positions at the time.

So, during the reign of Suharto is no longer a sense of shared responsibility but there is only mutual

advantage (Abdulgani, 2007). One of the proximity of the New Order was President BJ. Habibie well before he became president and after becoming president as the view (Winters, 2004), corruption in the government of President B.J. Habibie did two sectors at once, namely government and business.

To start the action of corruption collusion and Nepotism (KKN) it is done in Batam, put it the family and close friends in favorable positions. The corruption collusion and nepotism has become the soul in the power system established Soeharto, since, holding Supersemar. Power systems that are intended for business and collect "power resources" that could save personally and politically in power. Chronologically the development of corruption in Indonesia at the start of the formation of post-colonial countries, Hendaradi by Thantowi the period of parliamentary democracy, guided democracy, New Order, until after the end of the Suharto regime.

Corruption is still spreading entering the reform era Indonesia government, since, 2008, when the practice of corruption is increasing. Increased corruption can be obtained from historical data and various reports world institutions that engage in the issues of corruption and governance for example, Transparency international Asian Development Bank, World Bank, Corruption Perceptions Index, Gray Area Dynamics. Besides, the institutions that exist in Indonesia as KPK, ICW, CPC,

LBH and NGOs concentrate on the problems of combating corruption. Urgency combating corruption to save the state money from corruption. In the years 2003-2010 by the Commission IDR 8 Trillion. In the year 2011 by the Commission of IDR 134.6 billion, the potential loss of state oil and gas upstream IDR 152 trillion while in 2013 the Commission: 1:19 trillion to IDR 213 trillion of corruption prevention. And in 2014 the Commission, 2.8 T, AGO, IDR 792 billion, the Police and Total 3.66 67.7 Trillion (CPI, 2014 on Kompas Newspaper 6 November, 2015). The impact of corruption is also described by the Corruption Perception Index, shows that economic growth has been marred by corruption which is characterized by the abuse of power by leaders and high-ranking officials, "corruption perceptions. Index this puts Indonesia at rank 175 107 dari countries in the world.

This corrupt behavior greatly affects the competitiveness and quality of governance in Indonesia is still low when compared to Asian countries and other Asean. Indonesia's position in the World Competitiveness Yearbook 2014 is in 37th position with a score of 59.6. This position still lags behind its neighboring countries in Asia such as Hong Kong which exist in the 4-position with a score of 90.3, Taiwan at position 13 with a score of 81.2, Japan at position 21 with a score of 73.8, a neighboring clump of nearby, namely Malaysia which occupies the 12th position with a score of 82.1, China ranks 23 with a score of 73.3 and Korea at position 26 with a score of 69.7. In the Asean region, Indonesia is still lagging behind compared to Malaysia at position 12 with a score of 82.1, Thailand at the 29th position with a score of 65.0 or Singapore which ranks third in the world with a score of 91.0, far exceeding the countries in Asia except for Hong Kong which was within one ranked below Singapore. The only neighboring Asean strict sticking Indonesia is the Philippines which is in position 42 with a score of 55.0. When Indonesia's competitiveness on the world stage is still far behind countries in Asia and Asean in their own country was still not encouraging in terms of Governance Index or Governance.

Anti-corruption institutions such as ICW monitor corruption cases in 2015 there were 308 cases with 590 suspects. The total potential losses to the state of these cases reached 1.2 trillion rupiah and potential bribes amounted to 457.3 billion rupiah. The cases handled by Attorney at most for 211 cases (the potential losses to the state 815 billion rupiah and 550 million rupiah bribe potential). Followed by police who handled 86 cases with potential losses to the state amounting to IDR 310 billion and the value of bribes amounting to IDR 72 million). Lastly, the Commission handles 11 cases (the potential

losses to the state 106 billion rupiah and IDR 395 billion bribe potential). ICW also reported in the first half of 2015, the most widely used mode is an evasion (82 cases), misappropriation of budget (64 cases), abuse of power (60 cases) and markup (58 cases). Based on the monitoring results, the mode that is rarely done is illegal charges by (1 case), extortion (2 cases) and mark down (3 cases). Just like the previous year, in the first half of 2014, 99 cases of embezzlement dominate mode of corruption.

Corruption is done from various backgrounds, different actors. Officer or employee in the Ministry of Local Government and the perpetrators of the most widely named as a suspect (212), followed by actor whose background as a director, commissioner, consultants and employees of the private sector in the second position (97). Subsequently, 28 people background Village Head, Head and Head named as a suspect. In the next sequence of 27 Regional Head (Governor/Regent/Mayor), 26 head offices and 24 members of the DPR/DPRD/DPD is named as a suspect. Consequently, there are some efforts to face corruption but the measurement and the actual achievement is seen through exposing real cases and this phenomenon is difficult to measure since it has social features and committed secretly.

The statement of the problem: How Synthesis Combination Against Repressive Measures and Preventive Actions in Combating Corruption Bureaucracy in Indonesia?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Writing this study uses literature review in which a series of activities related to data collection methods literature, reading and recording and processing of materials research (Mustika, 2008). Sources of data in the research literature in the form of books, journals, Artical periodicals, government documents, sources on the Internet and various types of reports and documents (either unpublished or already published (Mustika, 2008; Eller and Dominic, 2008; George, 2008).

Some studies of corruption can be described in this study. According to the Warren explains that "we have a moral obligation not to leave our successors a severely impoverished word, one with exhausted resource, poisoned lands and water and no escape from poverty huge numbers of people". The harmful consequences of this very alarming cause of the country's leadership. If the main purpose of which is relied upon is an abuse of power in a country, it will have an impact on the loss of prestige in the country, weakening of social morals, the decline of

ethical standards in the administration of government, increasing political instability and social insecurity (Abdul, 2005). Corruption led to the failure of the government, hurt the country, the dignity of the ruler, the corrupt nature of the decline of confidence, unfair which is a reflection of the organization of the State.

Model preventive offers Trust (trust), Honesty, Transparency, Education, Ethics. Confidence (trust) in the wake not only the state officials but also oriented to the community that behaves normal, honest and based norms. These norms include the issue of values and justice, professional standards and rules of conduct or based on the code of ethics and standards of the profession of state officials. The consequence that the trust aims to create rules (rules) in the process of good governance. A network of trust needs to be developed in a bottom-up in order to avoid the abuse of power of the rulers.

There are seven strategies that should be applied in networks of government is; concealment (concealment) detects and avoids manipulation of power, dissimulation, feigning conformity by adopting some available public identity but minimizing both compliance and visibility of internal operations and resources, client age (ethics good), acquiring protection by intermediate authorities, Thus reducing compliance and visibility but usually at a price, predation, organizing enough externally effective force both to acquire resources and to defend against predation by others, enlistment (registration), active integration into an existing regime is available niches, bargaining, establishing relations with major political actors on the basis of mutual contingent consent, dissolution, destruction of an existing network departures through either incremental or collective dismantling.

Truth or honesty refers to aspects of character, moral and connotes a positive and virtuous attribute such as integrity, honesty and candor including candor on behavior and hand in hand with the absence of lies, deceit, infidelity and others; besides, honesty means trustworthy, loyal, fair and honest; Honesty appreciated in many ethnic cultures and religions (Rogers, 1964).

Similarly, the meaning of transparency is always attached to a process of preventing corruption transparency will qualify if they meet several key aspects, clarity of roles and responsibilities, the availability of public information, the opening of budget management, the guarantee of integration (Oliver, 2004). While education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and customs (Dewey, 1944). Last is the Ethics or moral philosophy as a branch of philosophy that involves systematizing, defending and recommending the concept of right and wrong behavior. Ethics comes from the

Ancient Greek word *ethos* which is derived from the word *ethos* (habit, "custom"). In axiology philosophy consists of a sub-branch of ethics and aesthetics, each associated with values. Some experts such as Paul and Linda (2006) and Kidder (2003) states that ethics is the study of the science of human character ideal or moral obligation. Ethics as a set of concepts and principles that guide us in determining what behaviors help or harm living beings. In the dictionary "the cambridge dictionary of philosophy" states that ethics are used by 'morality' and is sometimes used more narrowly which means the moral principles of a certain tradition, groups or individuals.

Repressive models offer some elements of the Commitments, Prevention Law, Political Will (Good Will) and the death penalty. Commitment is the ability and willingness to align private behavior with the needs, priorities and goals of the organization. Commitment as a way to develop goals or meet the needs of organizations that essentially put the mission of the organization of the personal interests. According to the commitment can also mean acceptance of a strong individual to the goals and values of the organization and individuals strive and researcher and have a strong desire to remain in the organization.

Various practice bribery that occurred in the state in the administration of government greatly weaken democracy and distort the market which eventually lead to loss of state (Stiglitz, 2007). The consequence is valid in any country and at any time can be experienced by the country, including in Indonesia. Deviations market prices, the collapse of the democratic process, financial and commercial risks are very influential in the increase of investment and the decline of moral and ethical society pullback (Senior, 2006).

Actions and behavior that deviates from these state officials can damage the joints of the nation because an act of corruption is the government's failure to achieve the objectives of the enactment of time to determine the criteria for different types of decisions, reduced the amount of funds that should be used for the general public, corruption have an adverse effect on officials another of the government agencies, very degrading official ruling, the state officials are an elite group that is already being corrupt broadly and deeply, the decline of public confidence in the justice attitude of government officials, Bayley (Lubis and James, 1985). The impact of acts of corruption will mess up the policy, the country's wealth is allocated only to the rich people, the military, civil service and Waraga disrupt the country and even lead to public cynicism as well as the instability of the government bureaucracy. Rose mentions that corruption can also lead to poverty. As a result of this corruption

affects the poor, namely; receive fewer social services; investment and infrastructure projects tend to ignore that helps the poor; high marketing costs, especially those related to both illegal and legal fees and decreased ability to break out of poverty due to the transmission of poverty. The phenomena that occur in the community and the government as a result of rampant corruption is highly fatal, if this is allowed, it will undermine the components of the State (society) as the pillars that support the implementation of the development process. Corruption will hinder the development process. Of course, the existence of corruption affecting public policy, in particular the impact of its policy in favor of a particular group or special (Abdul, 2005).

The main reason for the construction goes well only be done through the implementation of clean government free from corruption because corruption can hamper sustainable development. A phenomenon that occurs in the form; character and behavior blocking in collecting taxes that are used as development costs; the widespread attitude of sanctions and the lack of confidence in the government and the social fissures. This will scrape out the existence of the country's development and the existence of private actors themselves, Leff.

So, various phenomena that occur as a result of corruption described above has destroyed all areas of life, such as corruption in the political, economic, security, social, legal and human dignity and even the researcher of the state have been plagued by corruption have been entrenched. Actions taken, it is very detrimental to the state and advantageous for the officials themselves. So, corruption can also be referred to as using public institutions for personal gain.

So, many acts of state officials who use state facilities on behalf of private and group interests. This violates the public administration ethics because ethics do not accept the decision rights of people who are not his and is used as guidelines in performing the duties of the country. Using state facilities outside the provisions of the present administration of the government is regarded as an aberration or administrative corruption. Administrative corruption can occur in situations or contract granted in accordance with applicable regulations. Corruption occurs in situations of transactions that take place in violating regulations (Rose-Acknerman, 1978; Pope, 2007).

Thus, the phenomena of corruption are exposed, resulting in the abuse of state power and destroy the ethics of public administration in the country itself. Its meaning is corruption is an act of power that deviate from the established rules state for the sake of power, interests and personal gain, families, groups and certain affiliates who can determine a country's decision and

resulted in losses to the state. This may be demonstrated through several sources described foreign agencies concentrate on the problems of corruption in Indonesia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Repressive model against corruption: Corruption is an act of regression models and strategies to control corruption in ways after an official of acts of corruption. Various ways have to be done to free the country from the shackles of corruption in the administration of the government because this current era of corruption already is abnormal. To prevent acts of corrupt behavior is abnormal then the punishment was carried out by abnormal that begins with the dismissal of the officials and state officials are corrupt, reduced income, the death penalty if they take, use and affects a person to take the property rights of the state.

Aggravating punishment for the corrupt or repressive decisive action against corruption. For example, the death penalty, confiscate property that is owned, also can prevent corruption occurred. Because the death penalty has consequences on other authorities not to repeat acts of corruption. The existence of special measures to combat corruption of state officials. Borrow a phrase from Robert Harris in the context of corruption eradication, law enforcement requires a good knife to behead the corrupt (Harris, 2007). Even need a strong hand to use a knife and a steady nerve.

Knives are intended Harris are the views or arguments sharp treated masterful oratory art. The hand was none other than the rulers themselves who dared to unload cases of official corruption. And last nerve that is a strong character to face conflicts and manipulations of the criminals who are already highly skilled in building a network of bribes to clean his face. This means that corruption cannot be eradicated by indecision rulers but also corrupt and corrupting examined argumentative to expose the nature of evil under the light of public morality.

Surely shooting morality in view Harris had two reasons for law enforcement in combating corruption, namely: first, teach in the search for justice for legal cases involving the expertise of speech and debate but the art of rhetoric will be useful to many people if perpetuated for the sake of the search for truth and justice and not the interests of the mere. Sincerity moral law enforcers gave sharpness and positive influence on the content before the public rhetoric of seeking justice. Instead decay and falsehood liver bend the truth into hollow rhetoric that misleads the public. Second, Justice for enforcement of the welfare of the people, should be the goal of the rulers

in the practices of politics, not merely a means of legitimacy of the interests of power but rather a pure vision that drives a statesman, it can be said that justice for the welfare of society is a life-giving spirit of the republic while corruption is a poison that killed at least a republic from state officials to the people. Harris explained that the sin of corruption with the metaphor of “rotting fish from head to tail”. If this country wants to keep surviving, poison it had to be removed in a comprehensive manner so that, the social organism healthy and refreshed.

In realizing all major law enforcement to be commander in enforcing the various rules in governance. There is a kind of consensus consciously driven by law enforcement actors to make new breakthroughs in combating corruption. Deciding networking for the benefit of the ruling elite, mob justice as law enforcement actors in the spotlight is often poor in decision corruption cases. In the sense that, it encourages actors law enforcement should be with the good will of the officials concerned shall.

Goodwill (political will) not only carried out by law enforcement actors but the politicians in the House of Representatives also have the good will to always push the direction and policies of any decision taken. This decision is not based on the interests of the political elite rather concerned with the fate of the people. This is actually becoming the legislative agenda of the people’s representatives in the house in earnest.

The political will of the legislature in the fight against corruption should seriously consider the strength and strategy to always find a way out of the bondage of corruption. The approach of the strength of political will is done by: start with the approach of the ruling elite who understand the issues and opportunities of what to do with a community approach, namely the citizens help produce information on issues of abuse power in the social shutter mapping agencies. Environmental conditions of public officials who are in the midst of society as individuals would be viewed directly on the characters and real life.

In the approach political will against corruption repressive can be done through the institutional approach, namely reforming the strengths and determine more effective institutions, formations, access to information, research as well as an increased ability to open up the network to communicate with the public. Reform of transparency will help in strengthening political will. The result is to reduce and change the corrupt opportunities. In determining the actions and goals of individuals, groups and networks both internally and externally.

The fourth approach is a synthesis of an international approach in view of the repressive corruption this approach was instrumental in supporting the construction of a state fund. His power can control officials through international cooperation. Because the goals set forth in order to manage effective governance. This may have implications for the effective leadership and transparency in organizing the government. Or want the formation of a government free of corruption problems. To explain the strategy of repression model of corruption as the researcher described in Fig. 1.

Model repressive measures on top developed and adapted from some of the brilliant minds of experts to liberate the corruption of the government. Model repression of corruption proposed (Indrayana, 2008) with the rule of law and a rule of law that are ethical, meanwhile Kpundeh and Johnston (1995) stated the proposal with their good will (political will) government where support for the model of repression of corruption should conduct through the ruling elite, personal, community, institutional and international cooperation.

Another model which offered (Harris, 2007) in the repression of corruption by proposing several symbols for the actor to eradicate corruption ahead with requiring hands (ruler would dare dismantle retrospective case series of corruption), knives (arguments sharp and proficient) and nerve (a strong character to face conflicts and manipulations of corrupt).

Synthesis model reconstruction combination corruption:

The synthesis of these two ways in combating corruption described in the study strengthen institutions in the direction of reform to reduce rampant corruption authorities. Prevention and repression of corruption to be comprehensive and have a desire out of the bondage of corruption has a strong commitment, the courage to act to combat corruption, the rule of just law, upholds the ethics of state administration and togetherness among the people, the NGO anti-corruption (agence’s non-state) and the state acts to free themselves from corruption.

The theory developed anti-corruption prevention as a synthesis model (THATEE Model):

Trust (believe) it relates to the essential antidote speed deviations culture of corruption. Because most of the criminals did not make honesty in him as one antidote of acts of corruption. Honest (honest) it relates to the value of honesty individuals or state officials in performing administrative duties within the framework of the principles of the state. That is going to avoid the abuse of power. Transparency it relates to the disclosure of information the authorities in carrying out the tasks of the state (state

Fig. 1: Synthesis model development of anti-corruption

budget management, decisions and administrative. With the aim of changing from obscurity becomes clear and evident. Education, it relates to the notion of anti-corruption, education early in educational institutions of the country. Because education can change a person's mental and behavioral become better at performing their duties. Ethics (ethics), it relates to good deeds and bad deeds are executed ruler. Ethics can prevent corruption because ethics is always oriented to neutrality on an issue. Ethics can distinguish between individual rights and the rights of the state. Corruption is the abuse of power against the rights of nations and for the sake of personal interest. To understand the synthesis to reconstruct models blend in developing the theory of eradication of corruption as described below reseacher.

The THATEE Model developed from these writers is expected at least to reduce the corruption of public officials in the state governance in Indonesia. The fifth element that has not been applied to the authorities when it came to power. Meanwhile, repression of corruption requires the commitment of law enforcement, political will and international cooperation and even the death penalty (KPPH Model) be an alternative to free-growing proliferation of corruption in this country with severe punishments for the corrupt.

CONCLUSION

There are some synthetic that should be of concern in reconstructing blend of combating corruption by means of prevention and repression, among others: first, the concept of corruption is defined as the abuse of power by state officials for the benefit and harm the interests of the

ruling elite that the various elements of the state. Second, corruption can be started from the man would drive needs material and poor environmental agencies can influence the state authorities on the character and character for abuse of power. Third, corruption committed through the past to securing human nature (human nature) because basically corruption is part of the bad behavior of every human being.

Secondly, corruption is practiced by the rulers of the present era similar to the behavior of corruption in the kingdom where the authorities are not able to distinguish between private property and state property so that in carrying out the tasks of the state by entering preferences and personal interests that cannot be avoided. On the other hand, can control the power of the state in all dimensions of life, both economically, politically and financially on the basis of his authority.

Third as a synthesis in fighting corruption, the researchers developed a theory proposed that the fight against corruption, eradicate corruption by way of prevention can be done through some potential to be possessed; like, trust, honest, transparency, education and ethics (THATEE Model), even the involvement of state actors (government, legislative and stakeholder coalition) will strengthen the eradication of corruption in the future.

Fourth, synthesis for the action or the repression of corruption can be done through law enforcement and the actors involved (lawyers, judges, the judicial mafia, the authorities, employers and political elite). The ruler must be strong in fighting corruption action with ability and good will. This is done under the ruling elite, community,

institutional and international. Measures against corruption also require a strong hand, a sharp knife and a strong nerve to face a conflict of interest for corruptors

RECOMMENDATIONS

As synthesis in fighting corruption, the researchers suggested that eradicating corruption in Indonesia can be done in several ways prevention through strategic steps to be taken are: trust, honest, transparency, education and ethics (THATEE Model). This model should ideally be supported by the involvement of state actors (government, legislative and stakeholder coalition) so that it can succeed in the eradication of corruption in Indonesia.

Repression against corruption serves to support law enforcement against attorneys, judges, the judicial mafia, the authorities, employers and political elite in Indonesia. The success of eradication of corruption depends on the ability of a strong ruler in taking action to eradicate corruption by the good will of resources. The network should be built by the ruling elite, community, institutional and international. Measures against corruption in Indonesia is time symbolized by a strong hand, a sharp knife and a strong nerve to face a conflict of interest for corruptors.

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